

A Study of Spallation in Phenolic-Resin Based Woven Roving Glass Fibre Reinforced Composite Material

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ABSTRACT

Experimental investigation on spallation of phenolic-resin glass fibre reinforced composite were carried out under uniaxial strain using a gas gun. The stress wave, under precisely controlled condition, propagated along the normal to glass fibre mats. The results show that the threshold of spallation in the concerned material depends strongly on the duration of stress wave, especially for very narrow impulse. A spallation criterion for this composite is obtained and the prediction in terms of the given criterion is in good agreement with the experimental results. Finally, it seems that an incubation period for crack activation in this material exists.

INTRODUCTION

Phenolic-resin based woven roving glass fibre reinforced composite material has been widely used for structural components under dynamic as well as static conditions, but till now little research were carried out on its dynamic response to impulse load under precisely controlled condition especially on its fracture mechanism. In this paper spallation caused by stress wave propagating perpendicularly to the ply was investigated. Experimental results show that the spallation threshold of the concerned material depends strongly on the duration of stress wave and the threshold velocity increases with decreasing impulse duration, this becomes clear for very narrow impulse.

Based on spallation criteria of homogeneous material (see ref.1,2) and with some modification, a criterion predicting the incipient spallation of the aforementioned composite material was given.

EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES AND TESTED MATERIAL

Phenolic-resin based glass fibre reinforced composite material was used and tested at room temperature. Some mechanical and physical properties of the material are given in table 1.

Experiments were carried out on a light gas gun with $\phi 101$ mm calibre and barrel length of 17m. Specimen was fixed on the target holder near the muzzle of the gun as shown in Fig.1. Target specimen and flyer plate were casted on target ring and sabot using epoxy respectively. The tilt angle of impact was

controlled to be under 10^{-3} rad. After impact, both the specimen and flyer plate went into the hollow of the aluminum sabot being prevented from secondary damage and thus soft recovery was achieved.

TABLE 1 The mechanical and physical properties of phenolic-resin based glass fibre reinforced composite material

Density	1.64 g/cm ³
Density of cured phenolic-resin	1.17-1.18 g/cm ³
Static tensile strength of the composite under loading perpendicular to plies	5.7-5.8 MPa
Thickness of phenolic-resin layer between fibre plies	0.01 mm
Tensile elastic modulus of composite along the fibre direction	20400 MPa
5 plies per millimeter	

Special measures have been taken to keep the projectile velocity reproducible below 50m/sec which is the lower limit of muzzle velocity of the gun.

After impact, the recovered specimens were examined with ultrasonic detector. The least diameter of crack in the composite material which can be recognized with this technique is 8mm. Thus the threshold velocity for spallation is defined as the velocity beyond which a damage area larger than $\varnothing 8$ mm circle. The position of crack can only be determined along the radial direction of the specimen with this technique. After ultrasonic inspection, specimen were sectioned, polished and then observed under microscope. It was shown that crack position determined by the non-destructive testing agreed fairly well with the results observed under microscope.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Four groups of experiments were carried out with the results shown in table 2-5. The same composite material were used for both target and flyer. The thickness of target and flyer plates were different for different group but the thickness ratio between target and flyer was constant and approximately equaled to 2. The diameter of the target plates was 70mm, and that of the flyers was 75mm.

TABLE 2 Experimental results of group A

No. of shoots	Impact velocity (m/sec)	Tilt angle of impact (rad)	Thickness of specimen		Effect of spallation	Distance of spalled plane from the free surface (mm)	Results of ultrasonic inspection
			Flyer (mm)	Target (mm)			
81-109	37.0		7.2	14.5	A*	6.9	
81-70	36.7	9.6×10^{-4}	7.0	14.7	A*	8.75	
81-105	35.0	7.3×10^{-4}	7.0	14.1	B*	6.9	
81-71	34.4	2.5×10^{-3}	7.0	14.5	A*		
81-106	34.4	2.6×10^{-4}	7.0	14.65	A*	8.5	
81-72	33.7	1.1×10^{-3}	7.2	14.7	A*		
81-108	31.3		7.0	14.3	A*	8.3	
81-78	28.0		7.0	14.9	B*		
81-97	24.7		7.0	14.2	B*	6.4**	All area
81-98	21.8		7.2	14.8	D*	6.4**	All area
81-80	20.8		7.2	14.8	D*	8.6**	2cm ₂
81-81	20.5		7.3	14.8	D*	8.6**	2cm ₂
82-03	18.7		7.25	14.25	D*		1cm ₂

TABLE 3 Experimental results of group B

No. of shoots	Impact velocity (m/sec)	Tilt angle of impact (rad)	Thickness of specimen		Effect of spallation	Distance of spalled plane from the free surface (mm)	Results of ultrasonic inspection
			Flyer (mm)	Target (mm)			
81-110	41.5		3.7	7.3	A*	3.95	
81-111	40.3		3.7	7.3	B*	3.90	
81-188	38.0		3.4	6.5	D*		1cm ²
81-107	35.0	9.4x10 ⁻⁴	3.6	7.05	C*	3.45	All ₂ area
81-104	32.9	9.0x10 ⁻⁴	3.6	6.9	D*		3cm ²
81-115	31.0	1.2x10 ⁻³	3.3	6.5	C*		6cm ²
81-103	30.4	4.6x10 ⁻⁴	3.45	7.45	D*		No crack
81-102	28.6	9.9x10 ⁻⁴	3.5	6.3	D*		4cm ²
81-159	28.3		4.1	7.0	D*		No crack
81-156	28.2		3.3	7.2	B*	4.1	4/5 ₂ area
81-155	27.9		3.9	7.1	C*		1cm ²
81-158	26.9		4.0	7.0	D*		No crack
81-101	25.5	2.0x10 ⁻³	3.5	7.4	D*		2/3 area
81-185	23.9		3.5	7.2	D*		No crack
81-150	22.9		3.2	7.1	D*		"
81-144	17.5		3.9	6.3	D*		"

TABLE 4 Experimental results of group C

No. Of shoots	Impact velocity (m/sec)	Tilt angle of impact (rad)	Thickness of specimen		Effect of spallation	Distance of spalled plane from the free surface (mm)	Results of ultrasonic inspection
			Flyer (mm)	Target (mm)			
81-126	47.8		1.9	3.8	A*	1.28	
81-128	36.3		1.6	3.9	A*	1.55	
81-175	35.1		1.7	3.4	D*		No crack
81-157	34.1		1.5	3.5	D*		"
81-154	29.9		1.8	3.3	D*		"
81-176	29.6		1.6	3.2	D*		"
81-152	28.8		1.7	3.3	D*		"
81-153	27.6		1.5	3.2	D*		"
81-151	23.0		1.8	3.3	D*		"

TABLE 5 Experimental results of group D

No. of shoots	Impact velocity (m/sec)	Tilt angle of impact (rad)	Thickness of specimen		Effect of spallation	Distance of spalled plane from the free surface (mm)	Results of ultrasonic inspection
			Flyer (mm)	Target (mm)			
81-187	91.0		1.0	1.7	D*		1cm ²
81-184	88.8		1.0	1.75	B*	0.7	All ₂ area
81-183	79.8		1.0	1.7	D*		1cm ²
81-186	78.3		1.0	1.6	D*		No crack
81-182	69.3		1.0	1.5	D*		"
81-181	65.6		1.0	1.5	D*		"
81-180	48.8		1.0	1.7	D*		"
81-178	44.9		1.0	1.7	D*		"

A*-Completely separated B*-Visible spalled crack C*-Indistinct circumferential D*-No visible crack **-Internal crack, measured after sectioning. The area in the last column of table 2-5 is the area of internal crack in specimens which were determined by the ultrasonic detector.

Fig.2-5 shown micrographs of sectioned target specimens. Fig.2 is the original specimen. Cracks after impact are clearly shown in Fig.3 and Fig.4. Figure 5 is a fractograph under scanning electromicroscope which indicates that the fracture occurs at the interface between glass fibre and resin.

DISCUSSION

1 From table 2-5, the threshold velocity V_0 can be obtained. Since the thickness ratio in these four groups is constant and roughly equals to 2, the flyer thickness δ_p thus represent the impulse duration of tensil load in the target, and the characteristic curve of spallation can be simply expressed by the relation between V_0 and δ_p , as shown in Fig.6.

Fig.6 shown that the threshold velocity increases with the decrease of flyer thickness, especially for thin flyers. It means that the impact stress at threshold of spallation increases tremendously with the decrease of the duration of tensil load. Since the flyer thickness corresponds to the duration of tensil stress, it seems that there is a duration limit beyond that no spallation can occur.

2 Based on Fig.6 and related data, a spallation criterion for glass fibre reinforced phenolic-resin composite material was established.

For crack extension, phenomenologically it can be assumed that:

$$\frac{dl}{dt} = A l^{+m} (\sigma - \sigma_0)^n \quad (1)$$

while l is the crack length, t , the time, σ , the stress and σ_0 , a certain critical stress. σ_0 together with A , m and n are material constants. It means that the rate of crack propagation increases with the length of crack already existed and the stress level which has a certain lower value called σ_0 .

Integrate the equation (1), it shows that:

$$\frac{1}{(-m+1)} (l^{-m+1} - l_i^{-m+1}) / A = (\sigma - \sigma_0)^n (\tau - \tau_i) \quad (2)$$

If we define the initial spallation as the case while crack extends to a characteristic value, say $l=8mm$, then equation (2) becomes

$$(\sigma - \sigma_0)^n (\tau - \tau_i) = K \quad (3)$$

Equation (3) is considered as a suitable form of spallation for this material. In this formula, σ is the impact stress, and τ is the duration of stress σ , while σ_0 , n , τ_i and K are material constants which can be experimentally determined.

To simplify the related calculation, we assume: (a) No stress wave attenuation occurs in the material because of the thin target; (b) The shock wave velocity is considered as constant, because of the low impact velocity; (c) The rarefraction wave and reloading wave are both elastic waves. Then, the spallation criterion can be converted into another expression including v , δ_p and τ_t . Here v is impact velocity, δ_p is flyer thickness, τ_t is target thickness. And the related constants can thus be determined by plane impact experiments. In our case, we get: $\sigma_0=31.3$ MPa, $\tau_i=0.217$ μs , $n=1.345$ and $K=244.3$. Substituting the values of σ_0 , τ_i , n and K into equation (3), finally we determine the criterion as follows:

$$(\sigma - 31.3)^{1.345} (\tau - 0.217) = 244.3 \quad (4)$$

there σ in MPa and τ in μs . According to this criterion the predicted threshold velocity agreed fairly well with that determined by experiments.

3 Equation (2) contains two material constants l_i and τ_i which might not

be zero. If $\tau < \tau_i$, crack can not extend at all no matter how larg σ is. according to our experimental results, from equation (4), it shows that, at least, τ_i does exist and $\tau_i = 0.217 \mu s$. It seems that from $\tau = 0$ to $\tau = \tau_i$, there is an incubation period which might be important for improving the impact strength of composite material and worth to be further investigated.

CONCLUSION

1. Results of our investigation show that threshold velocity of spallation in phenolic-resin glass fibre reinforced composite material strongly increases with the decrease of flyer plate thickness and when flyer plate is thinner than 0.4mm, no spallation has been occurred.

2. An semi-empirical spallation criterion of the form of $(\sigma - \sigma_0)^n (\tau - \tau_i) = K$ was given in this paper. For the concerned material with experimentally determined material constants it becomes

$$(\sigma - 31.3)^{1.345} (\tau - 0.217) = 244.3$$

According to this criterion the predicted and actual threshold velocity agree fairly well.

REFERENCES

1 B. M. Butcher, L. M. Barker, D. E. Munson and C. D. Lundergan, "Influence of stress history on time --- dependent spall in metal" AIAA J. Vol.2, No.2 1964, pp.997
 2 F. R. Tuler and B. M. Butcher, "A criterion for the time dependence of dynamic fracture" Inter. J. Fracture Mech. Vol.4, No.4, Dec., 1968

Fig. 1 Schematic of plane impact experiment on gas gun

Fig. 2 Target before impact
no crack (x30)

Fig. 3
Impact velocity $V=20.5\text{m/sec}$
Target thickness $t=14.8\text{mm}$
Flyer thickness $p=7.3\text{mm}$
No. of shoots 81-81
(x75)

Fig. 4
Impact velocity $V=25.5\text{m/sec}$
Target thickness $t=7.4\text{mm}$
Flyer thickness $p=3.5\text{mm}$
No. of shoots 81-101
(x75)

Fig. 5
Impact velocity $V=37\text{m/sec}$
Target thickness $t=14.5\text{mm}$
Flyer thickness $p=7.2\text{mm}$
No. of shoots 81-109
(x500)

Fig. 6 Characteristic curve of spallation of phenolic-resin glass reinforced composite

